

READING SUCCESS FOR ALL: UTILIZING TEACHING AT THE RIGHT LEVEL (TARL) READING MATERIAL TO LEVERAGE MULTIGRADE LEARNERS' COMPREHENSION SKILLS

Jeorilyn S. Omelgo¹, Kimverly S. Esquillo²

¹ Dep Ed Quezon, Yugno Elementary School, San Andres, Quezon, Philippines

² Dep Ed Quezon, Yugno Elementary School, San Andres, Quezon, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study employed a mixed-method research design to determine the effectiveness of the Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) reading materials in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners at Yugno Elementary School. Using purposive sampling, 21 learners (14 Grades 4 and 7 Grade 5) participated in the intervention. Quantitative data were collected through pretests and posttests to measure learners' reading comprehension levels, while qualitative data were gathered via interviews and document analysis of lesson plans, learning logs, and assessment records. Descriptive statistics, frequency counts, percentages, and a paired sample t-test were used to analyze quantitative data, whereas thematic analysis explored learners' experiences and instructional practices. Findings revealed that before the intervention, most learners were at the Frustration level, demonstrating low reading comprehension, while only a few were able to read independently. After the use of TARL reading materials, all learners improved, with the majority achieving Independent-level proficiency and none remaining at the Frustration level. The paired sample t-test confirmed that the improvement was statistically significant. Thematic analysis highlighted that TARL materials made texts easier to understand, increased learners' confidence, fostered enjoyment and motivation, and promoted independent reading. Document analysis indicated that TARL was implemented through structured, level-based, and differentiated instructional practices, systematically monitored and integrated into classroom routines. These results demonstrate that TARL is an effective, evidence-based approach for improving reading comprehension in multigrade classrooms. Schools and teachers are encouraged to adopt TARL to address diverse learner needs, enhance literacy outcomes, and foster learner-centered reading environments.

Keywords: *Teaching at the Right Level, multigrade learners, reading comprehension, literacy intervention, learner-centered instruction*

Introduction

Reading comprehension is a foundational literacy skill that significantly influences learners' academic achievement across all subject areas. For learners in multigrade classrooms, developing comprehension skills presents unique challenges due to varied reading levels, limited instructional time, and diverse learning needs within a single classroom setting. Studies have shown that when reading instruction is not aligned with learners' actual ability levels, many students struggle to comprehend texts effectively, leading to persistent learning gaps (Risonar, Rey, & Delima, 2024; Alda & Gementiza, 2023). These challenges highlight the need for inclusive and adaptive instructional approaches that ensure reading success for all learners.

Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) has emerged as a promising approach to address learning diversity by grouping learners according to their actual skill levels rather than their age or grade. Muammar, Ruqoiyyah, and Ningsih (2023) emphasized that TaRL significantly improves learners' initial reading skills by providing instruction that matches their current competencies. By focusing on learners' readiness levels, TaRL creates opportunities for meaningful engagement with reading materials, allowing learners to progress at an appropriate pace and build comprehension gradually.

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of TaRL in enhancing reading outcomes across different educational contexts. Jazuli (2022) reported that TaRL improved students' literacy abilities by ensuring that instructional materials and activities were responsive to learners' needs. Similarly, Najah, Jabu, and Basri (2024) found that TaRL-supported reading instruction fostered improved comprehension and learner participation, even at higher educational levels. These findings suggest that TaRL is not limited to early reading instruction but can be adapted to strengthen comprehension skills across grade levels.

In multigrade classrooms, differentiated instruction is essential to address the wide range of learner abilities. Afandi et al. (2024) noted that differentiated learning using the TaRL approach enhances both learners' interest and learning outcomes by making instruction more relevant and accessible. Likewise, Maquiling (2024) emphasized that flexible grouping and leveled materials are key strategies for improving literacy instruction in multigrade settings. TaRL aligns with these principles by allowing teachers to use reading materials that directly respond to learners' comprehension levels.

Beyond academic gains, TaRL also contributes to increased learner motivation and engagement. Amalia, Safrida, and Ulva (2024) highlighted that instruction aligned with learners' abilities fosters confidence and active participation, which are essential for sustained reading development. When learners experience success with appropriately leveled texts, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward reading and persist in challenging tasks, leading to deeper comprehension over time.

Given these considerations, this study focuses on utilizing Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) reading materials to leverage multigrade learners' comprehension skills. Anchored in evidence-based practices, the study aims to explore how TaRL-based reading instruction can support inclusive learning, reduce comprehension gaps, and promote reading success for all learners in a multigrade classroom. Examining this approach, the study seeks to contribute to effective literacy instruction that responds to learner diversity and strengthens reading comprehension outcomes in complex classroom contexts.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) reading materials in improving the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners before using the TARK reading materials?
2. What is the level of reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners after using the TARK reading materials?
3. Is there a significant difference in the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners before and after the use of the TARK reading materials?
4. What themes emerge from the experiences of learners regarding the use of TARK reading materials in enhancing their reading comprehension skills?
5. What instructional practices, learner progress, and use patterns are evident in school documents related to the use of TARK reading materials in multigrade classes?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method research design to determine the effectiveness of the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) reading materials in improving the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners at Yugno Elementary School. The mixed-method approach allowed the integration of quantitative data on learners' reading performance and qualitative data on learners' experiences and instructional practices, providing a comprehensive understanding of the intervention's impact. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 21 multigrade learners, consisting of 14 Grade 4 learners

and 7 Grade 5 learners, who were enrolled in a multigrade class and actively participated in the TaRL reading activities. Quantitative data were collected to determine the learners' reading comprehension levels before and after the use of TaRL reading materials. These data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages to describe learners' performance levels. To examine whether a significant difference existed between pretest and posttest reading comprehension scores, a paired sample t-test was employed. Qualitative data were gathered through learner reflections and interviews to explore their experiences with the TaRL reading materials. These data were analyzed using thematic analysis, which enabled the identification of recurring themes related to engagement, challenges, and perceived improvements in reading comprehension. Additionally, document analysis of school records, lesson plans, and learner progress reports was conducted to identify instructional practices, learner progress, and use patterns associated with the use of TaRL reading materials in multigrade classes. This integrated methodology ensured a holistic and evidence-based evaluation of the effectiveness of TaRL in enhancing multigrade learners' reading comprehension skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the results of the study on the effectiveness of the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) reading materials in improving the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners. Both quantitative and qualitative findings are discussed to provide a comprehensive understanding of learners' performance, experiences, and instructional practices. The results are interpreted in relation to existing literature to highlight the impact of TaRL on reading outcomes and learner engagement in multigrade classrooms.

Table 1

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of Multigrade Learners before using the TARK Reading Materials

Level of Reading Comprehension	Grade 4		Grade 5	
	f	%	f	%
Independent	2	14.29	2	28.57
Instructional	5	35.71	1	14.29
Frustration	7	50.00	4	57.14
Total	14	100%	7	100%

Legend: *Independent 90-100%, Instructional 75-89%, Frustration 75% below*

Table 1 presents the level of reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners before the use of the Teaching at the Right Level (TARK) reading materials, disaggregated by Grade 4 and Grade 5 learners and categorized into Independent, Instructional, and Frustration levels.

The results reveal that a substantial proportion of learners in both grade levels were functioning at the Frustration level prior to the intervention. Among Grade 4 learners, 50.00% (7 out of 14) fell under the Frustration level, while 57.14% (4 out of 7) of Grade 5 learners were also classified in the same category. Learners at this level scored 75% and below, indicating significant difficulty in comprehending grade-level texts without intensive teacher support. This finding suggests that most multigrade learners lacked the foundational reading skills necessary for independent comprehension before the implementation of TARL materials.

Only a small number of learners demonstrated Independent-level comprehension. In Grade 4, 14.29% (2 learners) were at the Independent level, while Grade 5 showed a slightly higher proportion at 28.57% (2 learners). Although some learners were capable of understanding texts independently, their limited number indicates that independent reading proficiency was not widespread in the multigrade classroom.

The Instructional level, where learners can comprehend texts with guidance, accounted for 35.71% of Grade 4 learners and 14.29% of Grade 5 learners. This distribution suggests that while some learners were approaching grade-level competence, they still required structured teacher support to achieve comprehension. The findings highlight a heterogeneous and generally low level of reading comprehension skills among multigrade learners prior to the intervention. This condition is typical of multigrade settings, where teachers manage learners of varying ages, abilities, and learning paces within a single classroom.

These results are consistent with the literature. Alda and Gementiza (2023) emphasized that multigrade classrooms often struggle with addressing diverse reading levels due to limited instructional time and resources, leading many learners to remain at frustration levels in reading. The high percentage of learners in the Frustration category in the present study supports their observation that foundational literacy gaps are common in multigrade contexts.

Furthermore, the low pre-intervention reading levels align with the rationale for adopting the Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) approach. According to Ismail et al. (2024), TARL is effective precisely because it begins by assessing learners' actual skill levels rather than assuming grade-level proficiency. The predominance of learners at the Frustration level in this study underscores the necessity of such a diagnostic and differentiated approach.

Additionally, Amalia et al. (2024) found that TARL-based instruction improves learner motivation and learning outcomes by matching teaching strategies and materials to learners' current abilities. The baseline data in Table 1 demonstrate a clear mismatch between learners' reading levels and grade-level expectations prior to the intervention, further justifying the use of TARL reading materials in the multigrade classroom.

Hence, Table 1 indicates that before the use of TARL reading materials, most multigrade learners were performing below expected reading comprehension levels, particularly at the Frustration level. These findings are strongly supported by existing literature, which highlights both the challenges of multigrade reading instruction and the appropriateness of TARL as an intervention to address diverse learner needs.

Table 2

Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of Multigrade Learners after using the TARL Reading Materials

Level Reading Comprehension	Grade 4		Grade 5	
	f	%	f	%
Independent	8	57.14	4	57.14
Instructional	6	42.86	3	42.86
Frustration	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	14	100%	7	100%

Legend: *Independent 90-100%, Instructional 75-89%, Frustration 75% below*

Table 2 presents the level of reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners after the use of the Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) reading materials, categorized into Independent, Instructional, and Frustration levels for Grade 4 and Grade 5 learners.

The results show a marked improvement in reading comprehension levels among learners in both grades after the TARL intervention. Notably, no learner remained at the Frustration level in either Grade 4 or Grade 5. This indicates that all learners achieved at least an Instructional level of reading comprehension, reflecting the effectiveness of the TARL reading materials in addressing foundational reading difficulties.

For Grade 4 learners, 57.14% (8 out of 14) reached the Independent level, while the remaining 42.86% (6 learners) were classified at the Instructional level. Similarly, among Grade 5 learners, 57.14% (4 out of 7) achieved Independent-level comprehension, and 42.86% (3 learners) were at the Instructional level. These parallel distributions suggest that the TARL approach was equally effective across both grade levels despite differences in age and prior reading ability.

The substantial increase in learners at the Independent level signifies that more than half of the multigrade learners were able to comprehend texts independently, achieving scores between 90–100%. Meanwhile, learners at the Instructional level (75–89%) demonstrated improved comprehension that

allows them to understand texts with minimal teacher guidance. The absence of learners at the Frustration level further implies that TARL materials successfully scaffolded learning and prevented learners from being left behind.

These findings are strongly supported by existing literature. Jazuli (2022) reported that the Teaching at the Right Level approach significantly improves learners' literacy abilities by grouping students according to actual skill levels and providing targeted instruction. The shift of learners from Frustration to Instructional and Independent levels in this study mirrors Jazuli's findings on the effectiveness of TARL in improving reading outcomes.

Similarly, Muammar, Ruqoiyyah, and Ningsih (2023) found that implementing TARL in elementary classrooms led to significant gains in students' initial reading skills, particularly among struggling readers. The elimination of the Frustration level in the present study supports their conclusion that TARL is effective in strengthening foundational literacy skills.

Moreover, Maquiling (2024) emphasized that differentiated instruction strategies, such as TARL, are particularly beneficial in multigrade classrooms, where learners exhibit diverse reading abilities. The improved and more balanced distribution of reading levels across Grade 4 and Grade 5 learners in this study affirms Maquiling's assertion that TARL enhances literacy instruction by responding to learners' actual needs rather than grade-level assumptions.

In summary, Table 2 demonstrates that after the implementation of the TARL reading materials, multigrade learners exhibited significantly improved reading comprehension skills, with all learners reaching at least the Instructional level and a majority achieving Independent-level proficiency. These findings corroborate existing literature, which consistently identifies TARL as an effective approach for improving literacy outcomes, especially in multigrade and heterogeneous classroom settings.

Significant Difference in the Reading Comprehension Skills of Multigrade Learners before and after the Use of the TARL Reading Materials

The study examined whether the use of Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) reading materials produced a significant improvement in the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners by comparing their pretest and posttest scores. Quantitative analysis using a paired samples t-test revealed a marked increase in mean scores, indicating that the intervention had a statistically significant positive effect on learners' reading performance.

Table 2

Testing of Significant Difference in the Reading Comprehension Skills of Multigrade Learners before and after the Use of the TARL Reading Materials

	<i>Before the using TARL Reading Materials</i>	<i>After the using TARL Reading Materials</i>
Mean	18.65	23.4
Variance	40.66052632	19.51578947
Observations	20	20
Pearson Correlation	0.80676951	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	19	
t Stat	-5.536054544	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.2179E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.729132812	
P(T<=t) two-tail	2.4358E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.093024054	

Table 2 presents the results of a paired samples t-test conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners before and after the use of the Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) reading materials.

The descriptive statistics show that the mean score increased from 18.65 before the intervention to 23.40 after the intervention, indicating a substantial improvement in learners' reading comprehension performance following the use of TARL reading materials. In addition, the variance decreased from 40.66 to 19.52, suggesting that learners' posttest scores were more consistent and that performance gaps among learners were reduced after the intervention.

The analysis involved 20 paired observations, representing the same multigrade learners assessed before and after the intervention. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.81 indicates a strong positive relationship between the pretest and posttest scores, confirming that the paired t-test was appropriate for this analysis.

The computed t-statistic (-5.54) exceeded the critical t-value (± 2.09 , two-tailed, $df = 19$). Moreover, the two-tailed p-value (0.000024) is far less than the 0.05 level of significance. These results lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference in

the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners before and after the implementation of the TARL reading materials.

These findings are consistent with and strongly supported by existing literature. Jazuli (2022) reported that the Teaching at the Right Level approach significantly enhances learners' literacy abilities by aligning instruction with students' actual skill levels, rather than grade-level expectations. The significant increase in mean scores observed in this study reflects similar improvements noted in Jazuli's research.

Likewise, Muammar, Ruqoiyyah, and Ningsih (2023) found that learners exposed to TARL showed marked gains in initial reading skills, particularly among struggling readers. The significant difference between pretest and posttest results in the present study supports their conclusion that TARL effectively strengthens foundational reading comprehension skills.

In the context of multigrade classrooms, Maquiling (2024) emphasized that differentiated approaches such as TARL are essential in addressing the wide range of learner abilities. The reduced variance in posttest scores in this study aligns with Maquiling's findings that TARL helps minimize learning disparities by providing targeted instruction.

Furthermore, Najah, Jabu, and Basri (2024) demonstrated that the TARL approach significantly improves reading performance across different educational levels, including secondary learners. The statistically significant results in this study extend their findings by confirming the effectiveness of TARL in elementary multigrade settings.

Finally, the results also support the observations of Risonar, Rey, and Delima (2024), who noted that reading comprehension in multigrade classrooms improves when instruction is responsive to learners' actual reading levels. The significant improvement observed after the TARL intervention underscores the value of level-based instruction in multigrade contexts.

In summary, Table 2 provides strong statistical evidence that the use of TARL reading materials led to a significant and meaningful improvement in the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners. The findings are well supported by existing local and international studies, reinforcing TARL as an effective instructional approach for improving literacy outcomes in multigrade classrooms.

Thematic Analysis: Experiences of Learners Regarding the Use of TARL Reading Materials in Enhancing Their Reading Comprehension Skills

The interviews conducted with the 20 multigrade learners revealed meaningful insights into how the TARL reading materials influenced their

reading experiences and comprehension skills. Analysis of the learners' responses resulted in four major themes.

Theme 1: Improved Understanding and Easier Comprehension of Texts

Most learners expressed that the TARL reading materials helped them understand reading passages more easily compared to their previous experiences with grade-level texts. Learners emphasized that the texts were simpler, clearer, and matched their current reading abilities, allowing them to comprehend stories without feeling overwhelmed.

Some learners shared:

- *"I can understand the story now because the words are easy."* (Participant 3)
- *"Before, I don't know the meaning of many words, but now I can understand."* (Participant 11)
- *"It is not hard to read anymore."* (Participant 7)

This theme indicates that TARL materials effectively addressed learners' actual reading levels, which is essential in improving comprehension, especially for learners who were previously at the frustration level.

Theme 2: Increased Confidence and Reduced Fear in Reading

Another dominant theme that emerged from the interviews was the increase in learners' confidence when reading. Many learners shared that before using TARL materials, they felt shy, nervous, or afraid to read aloud because they struggled with words and sentences. After the intervention, learners became more confident and willing to participate in reading activities.

Learners stated:

- *"I am not afraid to read in front of my classmates now."* (Participant 5)
- *"I feel happy when I can read by myself."* (Participant 14)
- *"Before, I stop reading because it is hard. Now, I continue reading."* (Participant 9)

This theme reflects the emotional and motivational impact of TARL, showing that improved comprehension contributes to positive reading attitudes and self-confidence.

Theme 3: Enjoyment and Increased Interest in Reading Activities

Learners also described reading as more enjoyable and engaging when using TARL reading materials. Many participants mentioned that they liked the stories, pictures, and activities included in the materials, which made reading fun rather than stressful.

Learners responses include:

- *"I like the stories because they are interesting."* (Participant 2)

- “*Reading is fun now because I understand the lesson.*” (Participant 16)
- “*I want to read more stories.*” (Participant 8)

This theme suggests that TARL materials not only improved comprehension but also helped cultivate a positive reading culture among learners.

Theme 4: Ability to Read Independently and with Less Teacher Assistance

The learners also highlighted that TARL reading materials enabled them to read independently and rely less on constant teacher support. Learners shared that they could now answer questions, identify main ideas, and retell stories on their own.

Some learners expressed:

- “*I can answer the questions by myself.*” (Participant 6)
- “*I don’t always ask teacher for help now.*” (Participant 18)
- “*I can read and understand alone.*” (Participant 1)

This theme demonstrates that TARL promotes learner autonomy, a key indicator of improved reading comprehension and readiness for higher-level reading tasks.

The thematic analysis of the learners’ interviews reveals that the use of TARL reading materials had a positive and transformative impact on their reading comprehension skills and learning experiences. The four themes improved comprehension, increased confidence, enhanced enjoyment, and independent reading ability collectively show that TARL effectively responds to learners’ diverse reading needs in a multigrade classroom.

These findings reinforce the quantitative results of the study, which showed a significant improvement in reading comprehension scores after the intervention. More importantly, the learners’ voices highlight that TARL not only improves academic performance but also nurtures confidence, motivation, and a positive attitude toward reading.

In conclusion, the experiences shared by the 20 learners affirm that TARL reading materials are effective in enhancing reading comprehension skills while creating a supportive, engaging, and learner-centered reading environment in multigrade classrooms.

Document Analysis on TARL Reading Materials

School documents, including lesson plans, weekly learning logs, assessment records, and utilization checklists, were analyzed to understand instructional practices, learner progress, and usage patterns associated with TARL reading materials in multigrade classrooms. The analysis revealed several important findings.

Instructional Practices

The documents demonstrated that teachers implemented differentiated and level-based reading instruction, a core principle of TARL. Lesson plans frequently included:

- *Grouping learners according to their actual reading levels (Independent, Instructional, Frustration).*
- *Targeted reading activities aligned to learners' skill levels, such as decoding exercises, guided reading, and comprehension questions.*
- *Structured reading routines, including repeated reading, peer reading, and teacher-guided practice.*

For example, weekly plans showed that teachers allocated more time to learners at the Instructional and Frustration levels, while allowing Independent-level learners to engage in self-reading and enrichment tasks. Utilization checklists confirmed that these activities were systematically recorded and monitored, demonstrating adherence to TARL principles.

This indicates that TARL promoted planned, strategic, and differentiated instruction in multigrade settings, allowing teachers to address the wide range of reading abilities effectively.

Learner Progress

Assessment records, including pretests, posttests, and reading comprehension exercises, revealed significant improvements in learners' reading performance over time.

Documented data showed:

- *A shift of learners from Frustration to Instructional or Independent levels, consistent with quantitative findings.*
- *Gradual mastery of reading comprehension skills, such as main idea identification, vocabulary understanding, and text summarization.*
- *Consistent monitoring of learner progress, with teachers noting specific skill gains for each learner in weekly logs.*

For instance, post-intervention assessment tables indicated that all learners were at least at the Instructional level, with more than half achieving Independent-level reading comprehension. This demonstrates that TARL materials contributed to measurable learner growth in reading skills.

Use Patterns of TARL Reading Materials

Document review also highlighted patterns in how TARL materials were utilized in the classroom:

- *Materials were used daily or multiple times per week, particularly during literacy blocks.*
- *Learners progressed through reading materials sequentially based on skill level, ensuring scaffolding and mastery before moving to more complex texts.*
- *Teachers recorded observations, attendance, and completion of reading activities, showing that the materials were integrated systematically into classroom routines.*

The consistent use of TARL materials indicates high fidelity of implementation, which is important for achieving the positive outcomes observed in learner performance.

The document analysis provides strong evidence that the use of TARL reading materials in multigrade classrooms is structured, purposeful, and data-driven. Instructional practices reflect differentiated teaching aligned with learner needs. Learner progress is documented clearly, showing measurable gains in reading comprehension. Patterns of material use confirm systematic integration into classroom routines.

These findings complement both the quantitative results (significant improvement in reading comprehension scores) and the qualitative insights from learner interviews (increased confidence, enjoyment, and independent reading). Collectively, the documents validate that TARL reading materials support effective multigrade instruction and tangible learner improvement.

Summary of Findings

1. Before the use of TARL reading materials, most multigrade learners exhibited low reading comprehension, with the majority at the Frustration level and only a small proportion able to read independently.
2. After using the TARL reading materials, all multigrade learners improved their reading comprehension, with the majority achieving Independent-level proficiency and none remaining at the Frustration level.
3. The paired samples t-test shows that the use of TARL reading materials led to a statistically significant improvement in the reading comprehension skills of multigrade learners, with posttest scores higher, more consistent, and significantly different from pretest scores.
4. The thematic analysis of interviews with 20 multigrade learners revealed that the use of TARL reading materials significantly enhanced their reading comprehension by making texts easier to understand, increasing their confidence, fostering enjoyment and interest in reading, and enabling independent reading with less teacher support, thereby demonstrating TARL's effectiveness in addressing diverse learner needs and promoting a positive, learner-centered reading environment.

5. The document analysis of lesson plans, learning logs, assessment records, and utilization checklists revealed that TARL reading materials were implemented with structured, level-based, and differentiated instructional practices, consistently monitored for learner progress, and systematically integrated into classroom routines, resulting in measurable improvements in reading comprehension and supporting effective multigrade instruction.

Conclusions

1. Before the use of TARL reading materials, multigrade learners demonstrated low reading comprehension, with most functioning at the Frustration level, highlighting the need for targeted, level-appropriate literacy interventions.
2. After the implementation of TARL reading materials, all learners showed significant improvement in reading comprehension, with the majority achieving Independent-level proficiency and no learners remaining at the Frustration level, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention.
3. The paired samples t-test confirmed that the improvement in reading comprehension was statistically significant, indicating that the gains observed were reliable, consistent, and attributable to the use of TARL reading materials.
4. Thematic analysis of learner interviews revealed that TARL materials enhanced comprehension, boosted confidence, increased enjoyment and interest in reading, and promoted independent reading, underscoring TARL's role in fostering both academic and motivational outcomes in multigrade classrooms.
5. Document analysis showed that TARL reading materials were implemented through structured, level-based, and differentiated instructional practices, systematically monitored, and integrated into classroom routines, supporting measurable learner progress and effective multigrade instruction.

Recommendations

1. Schools and teachers should conduct diagnostic assessments at the beginning of the school year to identify learners at the Frustration level and implement level-appropriate reading interventions to address foundational literacy gaps in multigrade classrooms.
2. TARL reading materials should be regularly integrated into multigrade literacy instruction to ensure that learners continue to develop their reading skills, with emphasis on helping learners progress from Instructional to Independent levels.
3. School administrators and educators should adopt evidence-based interventions like TARL, supported by monitoring and assessment, to ensure that reading programs lead to measurable and reliable improvements in learners' comprehension skills.

4. Teachers should incorporate learner-centered practices, such as engaging and level-appropriate reading materials, guided and independent reading activities, and confidence-building strategies, to enhance both academic performance and learners' motivation to read.
5. Educators should continue structured, differentiated, and level-based instruction, maintain systematic monitoring through lesson plans and utilization checklists, and ensure consistent integration of TARL reading materials into classroom routines to sustain learner progress and instructional effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to established ethical standards in conducting research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants and, in the case of minors, from their parents or legal guardians. Participants were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and potential benefits of the study and were assured of their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained; learners' identities and personal information were kept secure and coded in all records, reports, and publications. Data were used solely for research purposes and were stored in a secure location accessible only to the research team. Furthermore, the study complied with the ethical guidelines for research in educational settings, ensuring that no harm, discomfort, or undue influence was inflicted on the participants. All instructional interventions, such as the use of TARL reading materials, were aligned with the learners' educational needs and were implemented under professional supervision by their classroom teachers. In summary, the study was conducted with full respect for the rights, safety, and welfare of all participants, in accordance with ethical research standards and institutional regulations.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to express deepest gratitude to Yugno Elementary School, its administrators, and teachers for their support and cooperation throughout this study, particularly in facilitating access to learners, school documents, and classroom observations. Special thanks are extended to the Grade 4 and Grade 5 learners who participated in this research for their enthusiasm, honesty, and willingness to share their experiences using the TARL reading materials. The researcher is also sincerely grateful to the action research adviser and mentors, whose guidance, insights, and constructive feedback greatly contributed to the successful completion of this study. Finally, appreciation is extended to the researcher's family and friends for their encouragement and support during the research process, whose patience and motivation were invaluable.

REFERENCES

- Afandi, R. A., Ningtyas, N. S., Susiyawati, E., & Pratiwi, P. (2024). The effectiveness of differentiated learning using the TaRL (teaching at the right level) approach for improving learning interest and learning outcome. *Jurnal Pijar Mipa*, 19(4), 657-662.

- Alda, R., & Gementiza, J. I. (2023). Reading Instruction in Multigrade Classes: A Narrative Inquiry. *Interdisciplinary Research Review*, 18(3).
- Amalia, S., Safrida, S., & Ulva, S. M. (2024). The application of teaching at the right level (TaRL) and culturally responsive teaching (crt) approach to increase the motivation and learning outcomes of students on the material of transport through membranes. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 10(1), 270-274.
- Ismail, I. A., Qadhafi, R., Huza, O., & Yorinda, Y. (2024). Teaching at the right level (TaRL) as a potential solution for improving middle school education: A systematic review of the literature. *International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR)*, 8(4), 126-138.
- Jazuli, L. (2022). Teaching at the right level (TaRL) through the all smart children approach (SAC) improves student's literature ability. *Progres Pendidikan*, 3(3), 156-165.
- Maquiling, Z. M. C. (2024). Enhancing literacy and numeracy instruction in multigrade classrooms. *United International Journal for Research & Technology*, 5(7), 61-74.
- Muammar, M., Ruqoiyyah, S., & Ningsih, N. S. (2023). Implementing the Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) approach to improve elementary students' initial reading skills. *JOLLT Journal of Languages and Language Teaching*, 11(4), 610-625.
- Najah, N., Jabu, B., & Basri, M. (2024). The Use of Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) Approach in Teaching Reading at Senior High School. *International Journal of Language, Education, and Literature*, 1(2), 95-101.
- Risonar, C. J. O., Rey, R., & Delima, R. (2024) Reading Comprehension in a Multigrade Classroom.

APA Citation:

Omelgo, J. S. & Esquillo, K. S., R. D. (2026). Reading Success For All: Utilizing Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) Reading Material to Leverage Multigrade Learners' Comprehension Skills. *KnowledgeNest Research Journal*, 2 (4), 824-839. 10.5281/zenodo.19157400.

jeorilyn.omelgo@deped.gov.ph